

Studies in Mixed Ligand Complexes. Part II

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Formation constants of the mixed ligand complexes, MAL, where M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II); A = Histidine, Iminodiacetic acid (IMDA) or Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) and L = Ethylenediamine or Propylenediamine have been determined by using an extension of Irving-Rossotti titration technique. The values obtained for the mixed ligand formation constant K_{MAL} are found to be 1.5 unit lower than the first formation constant K_{ML} in binary system. The smaller difference in $K_{MAL}^{MA} - K_{ML}^M$ can be explained by considering that the secondary ligand is neutral. The greater difference in CuNTAL complexes is due to Jahn Teller effect.

THE solution studies of mixed ligand complexes (MAL) where A = Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA), or Histidine or Iminodiacetic acid (IMDA) and L⁻ is a charged ligand ion have been carried out earlier¹⁻⁶. Here the attempt has been made to study the system (MAL), where L is a neutral base. Tondon and coworkers⁷ have also studied such systems using the method suggested by Thompson and Loraas. Bennett and coworkers⁸ have studied the system CuIMDAen by using another method.

As an extension of our work on the application of Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁹ to mixed ligand complexes, the study of the systems (MAL) where M = Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺; A = Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA), Histidine, Iminodiacetic acid (IMDA), and L = Ethylenediamine or Propylenediamine is being presented here.

The formation constants K_{MAL}^{MA} have been determined using two methods⁹ i.e., titration of M+A+L mixture against alkali and titration of the mixture M+A against concentrated solution of the basic ligand L.

The necessary condition for such a study is that the formation of M+NTA¹ or Histidine¹⁰ or IMDA 1 : 1^{11,12} complex formation should be complete at low pH and the 1 : 1 complex [MA] should be stable at higher pH where the combination of aliphatic amine takes place. The condition holds good in the present systems as has been observed, earlier⁶. The mixed ligand formation constant can be represented as follows :

$$K_{MAL}^{MA} = \frac{(MAL)}{(MA)(L)}$$

Experimental

Histidine (E. Merck, pure), NTA (Cornbrooks, England, pure), IMDA (BDH reagent) were used as primary ligands. Ethylenediamine and propylenediamine (A.R. Fluka) were used as secondary ligands. Metal perchlorates were prepared from the corresponding carbonates and the metal contents were

determined and checked. Other reagents used were perchloric acid (Baker analysed), sodium perchlorate (Fluka pure), sodium hydroxide (Chemapol). All solutions have been prepared in conductivity water.

Metrohm pH meter Model E 350 A (accuracy ± 0.05 pH units) was used and the titrations were carried out at 30°, using constant temperature bath (accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Following solutions were prepared. Volume was raised to 50 ml. in each case. The ionic strength of each solution was initially made 0.2M.

For Histidine : 1st method :

1. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M perchloric acid + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.176M sodium perchlorate.
2. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M histidine + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.178M sodium perchlorate.
3. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M perchloric acid + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.174M sodium perchlorate.
4. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M histidine + 0.178M sodium perchlorate.
5. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M histidine + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.176M sodium perchlorate.
6. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M perchloric acid + 0.178M sodium perchlorate.

For IMDA : 1st method :

1. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.004M perchloric acid + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.174M sodium perchlorate.
2. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M IMDA + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.174M sodium perchlorate.

3. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.004M perchloric acid + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.172M sodium perchlorate.
4. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M IMDA + 0.178M sodium perchlorate.
5. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M IMDA + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.176M sodium perchlorate.
6. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.004M perchloric acid + 1.176M sodium perchlorate.

For NTA : 1st method :

1. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.006M perchloric acid + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.172M sodium perchlorate.
2. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M NTA + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.174M sodium perchlorate.
3. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.006M perchloric acid + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.176M sodium perchlorate.
4. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M NTA + 0.178M sodium perchlorate.
5. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M NTA + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.176M sodium perchlorate.
6. 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.006M perchloric acid + 0.174M sodium perchlorate.

For Histidine : 2nd method :

1. 0.1M perchloric acid + 0.004M perchloric acid + 0.096M sodium perchlorate.
2. 0.1M perchloric acid + 0.004M histidine + 0.004M metal perchlorate + 0.092M sodium perchlorate.

For IMDA : 2nd method :

1. 0.1M perchloric acid + 0.008M perchloric acid + 0.092M sodium perchlorate.
2. 0.1M perchloric acid + 0.004M IMDA + 0.004M metal perchlorate + 0.092M sodium perchlorate.

In case of (M.NTA.L) systems, second method could not be applicable because it is not possible to prepare solution of NTA having concentration more than 0.02M as required in 2nd method. With dilute solution of NTA, separation of curve 1 and curve 2 in Fig 2 is very less and so there are chances of errors. 2nd method is also not possible in cases of Cd complexes containing histidine and IMDA (as primary ligand) because here separation takes place in very high pH range.

In the 1st method the above solutions were titrated against standard 0.2M alkali and pH was plotted against the volume of alkali. The representative plots in case of Ni.Histidine. en has been presented in the Fig. 1. The curves in other cases are of the same type.

Fig. 1. Ni-Histidine ethylenediamine at 30° (First method)

1. Acid + secondary ligand
2. Acid + histidine + metal + secondary ligand
3. Acid + metal + secondary ligand
4. Acid + histidine.
5. Acid + metal + histidine.
6. Acid.

In the 2nd method the above solutions were titrated against 1.0M secondary ligand (amines). The volume of secondary ligand was plotted against pH. The representative plot in case of [M.Histidine.en] system has been presented in Fig. 2. In the 1st method in the curve (1), curve (3) and curve (6) Fig. 1, one, two and three equivalents of extra acid have been added in case of histidine, IMDA and NTA, respectively, in order to account for the extra-hydrogen ions liberated due to the combination of the primary ligands, histidine, IMDA or NTA with the metal ions.

Similarly in the 2nd method, in the curve (1), Fig. 2., one and two equivalents of extra acid have been added in case of histidine and IMDA, respectively.

It is observed from curve (5) and curve (6) of Fig. 1 that the MA is formed at low pH. It undergoes hydroxocomplex formation at higher pH. The curve (2) remains merged with curve (1) at low pH showing that complexation of the aliphatic amine does not take place at low pH. Curve (2) diverges from curve (1) at higher pH showing that MAL combination takes place where MA 1:1 complex formation is complete. In this range hydroxocomplex formation also does not start. The horizontal distance between curve (1) and curve (2)

Fig. 2. Metal Histidine ethylenediamine at 30° (Second method).

- 1. Acid.
- 2. Acid + histidine + metal.

corresponds to the amount of secondary ligand which gets bound with MA and so \bar{n} and pL can be calculated using same equation as in earlier case⁹. \bar{n} corresponds to average number of L bound to MA. Precise values of K_{MAL}^{MA} were obtained by using the method of averages¹³. The values thus obtained have been presented in Table 1.

In the second method Fig. 2, curve (2) is slightly above curve (1) upto—3.5 to 6 pH (in different systems) because the coordination of A is not complete and it absorbs protons from solution. In the high pH range i.e., after—3.5 to 6 both the curves overlap showing that (MA) 1 : 1 complex formation is complete and after that curve (2) diverges from curve 1 showing that the combination of added ligand (L) starts with MA at that pH. From the horizontal distance between these two curves \bar{n} and pL can be calculated⁹.

It is observed that the values of K_{MAL}^{MA} obtained by both the methods give almost identical values.

The two methods are entirely different. The identity of the results indicates that the considerations made are valid. The values are also in close agreement with the values reported in some cases by other workers using different methods⁷⁻⁸.

The mixed ligand formation constant K_{MAL}^{MA} where L = ethylenediamine are less than those where L = propylenediamine. This is in accordance with the basicity of the ligands.

Histidine exhibits bi- or tri-dentate character¹⁰, coordination taking place from COO⁻ and from N of the imidazole or two nitrogens from both imidazole and amino groups. IMDA behaves as a tridentate ligand¹¹ coordination taking place from the N and two carboxylate oxygens¹². NTA behaves as a tri-⁴ or quadridentate⁴ ligand, coordination taking place from N atom and two or three COO⁻ groups, respectively.

The 1 : 1 complexes of these multidentate ligands are stable at high pH, remaining coordination position

TABLE 1. MIXED LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 30°.

	K_{NiAen}^{NiA}		K_{NiApn}^{NiA}		K_{CuAen}^{CuA}		K_{CuApn}^{CuA}		K_{ZnAen}^{ZnA}		K_{ZnApn}^{ZnA}		K_{CdAen}^{CdA}		K_{CdApn}^{CdA}	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Histidine	6.38	6.48	6.65	6.70	—	—	—	—	5.21	5.23	5.39	5.46	4.87	—	5.16	—
IMDA	6.33	6.34	6.95	7.03	9.05	9.09	9.19	9.23	5.10	5.13	5.65	5.69	4.62	—	5.08	—
NTA	5.35	—	6.96	—	7.64	—	8.23	—	4.69	—	5.15	—	4.85	—	5.08	—

around the metal ion being occupied by water molecules. A secondary ligands can replace the water molecules to form mixed ligand complex MAL.

In the study of mixed ligand complexes containing such charged primary ligand ions and secondary ligand ions with negative charge⁶, it has been observed that K_{MAL}^{MA} is very much lower than K_{ML1}^M . This is because of the repulsion between the incoming charged ligand ion and the already existing charged ion. However, it is observed that in the present study of these systems with Histidine, IMDA, NTA as primary ligands, the values of K_{MAL}^{MA} are not very much lower than K_{ML1}^M values. This is because the incoming secondary ligands are neutral bases and so there is no coulombic repulsion as observed in cases^{6,10} where secondary ligand is a charged one. Formation constants of the ternary systems are lowered to some extent due to statistical factors and probably due to steric hindrance.

It is, however, observed that though formation constants of binary copper complexes of the bases are higher than the formation constants of Ni complexes by $3 \sim \log$ units, the difference $K_{CuAL} - K_{NiAl}$ is only ~ 1.3 , where A = NTA. This can be explained in terms of Jahn-Teller distortion¹⁴, as done in previous publications⁴.

However, in $CuIMDAen$ or pn systems the values of K_{CuAL}^{CuA} are not very much lowered indicating that IMDA occupies two positions in the equatorial plane and one along the axial direction, thus leaving two positions in the equatorial plane vacant for the secondary ligand to occupy.

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